

Les principaux piliers stratégiques pour une agilité organisationnelle en temps de crises économiques et sanitaires.

The main strategic pillars for an organizational agility in times of economic and health crises.

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Résumé

Cet article analyse les principaux piliers stratégiques pour une agilité organisationnelle en période de crise économique et sanitaire. Un concept d'actualité qui permet de faire face aux incertitudes économiques, sociales et environnementales réelles rencontrées par les organisations. De nos jours, la gestion de crise et l'agilité sont considérés comme un défi pour les entreprises dans un monde fortement caractérisé par des incertitudes, des changements et la complexité des procédures et réglementations. De ce fait, les organisations doivent mettre en place des procédures de gestion de crise et des plans d'action régulièrement mis à jour, en prenant en compte les technologies en pleine expansion et les nouvelles approches managériales en vigueur.

Les crises doivent être anticipées et les entreprises doivent être préparées à tous leurs éventuels impacts financiers, économiques et sociaux. Ainsi, il est important de définir et d'analyser le concept d'agilité organisationnelle afin de comprendre ses implications et ses leviers.

De précédentes recherches ont défini l'agilité comme la capacité d'une entreprise à mettre en œuvre rapidement une reconfiguration organisationnelle pour répondre à un changement. Néanmoins, l'agilité organisationnelle doit prendre en compte toutes les composantes clés d'un processus de gestion du changement afin d'exploiter, en toute situation et en temps réel, toutes les opportunités offertes par le changement.

Ce présent article présente les concepts clés à analyser au sein d'une organisation pour obtenir des processus flexibles et des performances élevées. Il propose également les principaux leviers stratégiques pour assurer une agilité organisationnelle au sein des entreprises, en temps de crise. De ce fait, nous avons mobilisés un ensemble de théories d'organisation qui permettent de comprendre les principaux leviers de performance d'une organisation et d'identifier les piliers nécessaires pour mettre en place une stratégie d'agilité organisationnelle. Notamment, le modèle 7S de McKinsey qui met en évidence le système, le personnel, la stratégie, le style de management, les compétences, la structure et les valeurs communes partagées au sein d'une organisation. Nous avons ensuite analysé les actions à entreprendre dans différentes situations d'incertitudes selon le modèle Cynefin développé par David Snowden en 1999.

Finalement, nous démontrons que grâce à la mise en œuvre des dix facteurs d'agilité organisationnelle développés au niveau de l'article, les entreprises vont réagir de manière plus efficiente et rapide aux changements et seront plus performantes en temps de crise économique et sanitaire.

Mots clés : Agilité, Agilité organisationnelle, Changements, Crises, Incertitudes, Piliers stratégiques, Reconfigurations organisationnelles.

Abstract

This article analyses the main strategic pillars for an organizational agility in times of economic and health crises. A concept that makes the headlines to aid the actual economic, social and environmental uncertainties encountered by the organizations. Nowadays, crisis management and agility is a critical exercise and challenge for firms in a world, that is highly characterized by uncertainties, changes and complexity. For that, organizations must implement crisis management procedures and plan of actions; that are regularly updated; by taking into consideration the fast growing technologies and the new managerial approaches. Crisis must be expected and firms must be prepared for all their eventual financial, economic and social impacts. For that, the concept of agility is important to be defined and analysed to understand its implication and levers. Previous researches defined the agility as the capacity of a firm to implement quickly an organizational reconfiguration in order to respond swiftly to a change. For that, organizational agility must consider all the key components of a change management process in order to exploit, under any situation, and in real-time, all the opportunities offered through the change.

This paper reviews the different key elements to analyse within an organization for flexible processes and high performance through the 7S McKinsey model. The model describes how agility can be achieved in an organization thanks to seven key elements: Systems, staff, skills, shared value, structure, style and strategy. It also analyses the actions to take in the different situations of problems and uncertainties according to the Cynefin Model instituted by David Snowden in 1999. An organization must be able to categorize a situation by defining its causes and effects in order to execute an adapted agile strategy. Furthermore, we demonstrate in this paper that through the implementation of the ten developed enablers of organizational agility, the culture of adaptability will improve, and the firms will respond quickly to changes and attend efficiency in times of economic and health crises.

Keywords: Agility, Changes, Crisis, Organizational agility, Organizational reconfiguration, Uncertainties, Strategic pillars

Introduction

The global economy has been considerably buffeted by the recent economic and pandemic crises. Therefore, both economic and social environment became vulnerable, complex and unstable for all organizations.

During the pandemic of COVID-19, we noticed that several changes had been made for a short period to face the social, financial and logistic issues. Collaborative and innovative approaches were the key actions to find real-time alternatives and solutions for a continuous development of the activities. As a matter of fact, most organizations were designed for efficiency, not agility. The strategies are used to be established in order to obtain a maximum yield by running key activities efficiently. But nowadays, we must consider “Agility” as a constant lifestyle for all businesses by being able to attend their performances under any economic climate or conjuncture.

The causes and effects are no longer linear due to the complexity of the current socio-economic environment. Stakeholders are multiple and increasingly demanding. Agility must be seen as a management tool which influence the organizational structure, decision-making and the operations mode of the organization. We suggest that agile organization are those built through new ways of operating, by adapting their business models to a wider ecosystem and pursuing alternatives for possible scenarios of uncertainties and crises.

This paper reviews the concept of organizational agility and develop a conceptual framework grounded on ten pillars based on the existing literature on organization thinking and agility. We first define and analyze the different levels of “agility” under different degrees of uncertainties to face. A situation can be either evident, complicated, complex or chaotic. Therefore, we propose an agile managerial approach that take into consideration this categorization by using theoretical approaches as the McKinsey “7S” model and the Cynefin framework. We will also use pragmatic existing approach as “OODA Loop” to develop the proposed framework. Therefore, we identify the importance of the implementation of a digital strategy to support all the information flows that are produced within the firm. Automation of procedures and Big Data afford real-time and strategic information to transform into “InfoAction”. It allows organization to react efficiently to new challenges and requirements of a new situation. Finally, we highlight the importance of the development of a collaborative approach to make decisions by involving all the concerned parties essentially those who produce, collect and receive the information: From the supplier to the client.

A regularly review of the action plans and strategies insures confidence within the organization and the ability of adaptation.

1. Organizational agility: evolution or revolution?

The first section reviews the different concepts related to the notion of agility within an organization, its evolution and the enforcing elements for the implementation of an organizational agility.

1.1.Theoretical Background

The flexibility of organizations is inspired by old concepts such as learning organizations developed by Senge [1] or adhocracy by Mintzberg [2]. Those concepts emphasize structural coordination and cooperation to integrate for the deployment of strategic approaches based on adaptation and continuous improvement.

The concept of organizational agility emerged in 1995 with Goldman, Nagel and Preiss [3]. It was defined as the company's ability for continuous adaptation to external uncertainties due to the complexity of the environment. It represents the capacity to react quickly to a changing situation and mastering it through significant abilities for anticipation, innovation and adaptation (R. Dove, 2001) [4]. While the driving forces for change are increasing overtime; such as high speed innovation, globalization, economic uncertainties ... the liability of continuous "newness" as described by Hannan and Freeman in 1984 [5]; has become the cost of remaining competitive and ultimately, for the organization survival.

Implementing a culture of innovation within an organization involves a continuous evaluation of processes, employees, systems and plan of actions. It is a management approach to consider on order to find constantly new ways to perform activities (A. Harraf, 2013) [6].

The concept of agility is still the subject of actual debates. It represents the new real approach to improve the performance of the organization and reinforce its resilience to any external risk or uncertainty. The multiple models and definitions reviewed to capture the concept of agility highlights the necessity to investigate in new methods and merge multiple existing approaches adapted to the new challenges and existing resources.

Essentially, it is the capability to implement flexible structures and processes and to employ the coherent resources in the shortest possible times (Zerfass et al., 2018) [7]. The principal issue is to find how to transform organizations, having grown as oriented for efficiency, into flexible, learning organization having the required capacity to implement waves of renewal through its

development. Recent research about the agile organization model; developed by Chita in 2008 [8] defines four enforcing elements of organizational agility: Leadership, culture, Career and architecture. Those elements provide a constant dynamic interplay between organizations, and their environment.

Figure n°2: Conceptual model of agile organization

The first concept of leadership agility requires a tolerance for change and the capability to manage paradox and uncertainties. The objective is to achieve performance and transformation under any situation. The second element is important because cultural agility is needed for a strategic commitment in a diverse organization. For business agility, it is about flexible operating modes and nimblest organization structures. Finally, all those elements must be supported and executed by agile talent with a culture of innovation and a propensity for continuous change. For the ecosystem which is the environment or the situation, there is various theoretical model to analyze it. In order to understand the agile organization model above, we must describe the contexts (environment) that require an agile strategy and organization. Agility depends on the level of the complexity of the contexts and situations.

1.2.Organizations thinking and the Cynefin model

Uncertainties and problems can't be solved in one-size-fits-all method. The actions to take depend on the complexity of the situation and the level of control on their impact. The Cynefin Model, proposed by David Snowden in 1999, and republished in 2007, represent the most referenced framework to describe and categorize a situation or problem. It defines the four areas

of intervention according to our level of knowledge about the causes and effects of the situation.

Figure n°2: The Cynefin Model developed by David Snowden

Source: Cynefin model by D. Snowden

On the complex situations, it is impossible to identify one “correct” cause-and-effect relationship and one coherent solution. It is the sphere of “unknown unknowns” to which much contemporary situations has shifted due to the massive uncertainties within actual markets. Complex situations are unpredictable.

For that, organizations must Probe, Sense and then Respond rather than trying to control the situation by implementing a pre-defined plan of actions. According to the Cynefin Model, it’s often right to employ various probes to collect feedbacks on what are the best solutions for the context. Then, to look for new patterns so as to set an adaptive solution to emerge.

For the chaotic context, it is the sphere of “Unknowable”. There are no visible cause-and-effect relationships because they shift constantly and the “one” solution is unknown. Climatic catastrophes, crisis scenarios often fall into this context. The priority in this type of situation is to establish order and stanch the bleeding. The decision model for chaotic context is to Act, Sense the influence and impacts of the action, and finally respond coherently to move the situation from the chaotic context. A risk analysis is required to identify possible risks and

categorize them by evaluating their criticality. The two contexts above necessitate an organizational agility to attend performance within any context of crises or uncertainty.

The third context is defined as complicated; also called the domain of experts. The relationship between cause-and-effect is clear but it may not be visible to all the concerned parties, because the problem is complicated. It is the realm of “known unknowns”. The decision-making process is to Sense, analyse what is known and Respond using the good practices.

In the obvious context, cause-and-effect relationships are apparent to all the concerned parties and the options are clear. The situation is characterized by stability, and the right respond is evident and undisputed. This context requires straightforward management. Involved parties must Sense the facts of the situation, categorize them and Respond with established practices.

Analysing the Cynefin framework provides a different lens through which organizations can interpret situations and to appropriate an organizational agility in facing different contexts. There remains, therefore, to review the different key elements to analyse within an organization for an agile organizational design and high performance.

To develop furthermore our paradigm, the analytical framework will be inspired by the McKinsey “7S” Model, that describes how effectiveness and agility can be achieved in an organization. The seven key elements of the model are: Systems, staff, skills, shared-value, structure, style and strategy.

In order to perform the 7S analysis, the table below summarizes the main questions that should be considered while implementing an organizational agility framework. It allows to discern the forces of the organization for change and the forces against the change.

Table 1: Domains to harmonize for organizational agility

Domains harmonise to	Questions to be asked
System	-What are the processes, procedures and operating modes implemented by the organization? -What are the DATA and information management systems used by the organization? -How the organization fixes its financial resources?
Staff	-Are the employees implicated on the decision-making process? -Is there an inter-team coordination while executing an action? -Is there lack of human resources or capacity within the organisation?
Skills	-What are the skills that the employees detain to afford a high quality of your products and services? -Are the current skills of your employees sufficient to attend performance and flexibility? -How are the skills monitored and reinforced in the organization?
Shared-Value	-What are the common shared values of the organization? - How does this shared values transcends all the organizational levels of the firm?
Structure	-How is the business organized? -What is the decision-making process of the organization? -How information is shared within the organization?
Style	-What is the style of leadership adopted? -What is the attitude of employee towards top management? -Are the stakeholders working collaboratively or cooperatively?
Strategy	-What are the strategic objectives of the firm? -What are the special characteristics of the organization? -How does the organization adapt to fluctuations and changes in the Market?

2. The pillars of organizational agility

This section develops the factors that enhance the level of agility within a company based on both the 7S Mckinsey model and the pre-defined aspects of organisational agility.

The pillars of organizational agility are important to develop in order to provide simplified tools that can be used by different organizations, in different situations.

The interrelationship between the pillars is evident because of their interrelatedness to attend organizational performance and nimbleness. Embracing agility requires asking some relevant questions: What are the factors that determine the level of agility within an organization? How are they executed and supported? and what are their impact on organizational performance?

2.1.Tolerance for change and ambiguity

This first pillar is vital for an organization to thrive in complex and changing environment. It represents a mindset and an inherent culture that must transcends all the organizational levels.

Organization must be prepared for unpredictable situations by preparing in advance coherent responses to different problematics at different times. Several theories demonstrate the importance to take into consideration ambiguity in the decision making.

Basically, it is about making different interpretations concerning a content and its implications. Klinke and Renn (2002)[9] considered ambiguity as something that cannot be assessed objectively (i.e.: complexity) or for which we lack sufficient scientific knowledge (i.e.: uncertainty).

Nowadays, organizations must develop a “fitness” while reaping and interpreting the extensive existing information in the market. They must develop a tolerance regarding the fact that multiple interpretation can exist whether evident or not.

The real challenge is the capability to quickly alter the decision-making processes and information-collecting processes by selecting the relevant and coherent Data to respond coherently to the new requirements.

2.2. Agile strategy

In order to remain a flourishing structure and retain their competitive advantages, organizations must embrace a continuous strategic change adapted to the requirements of the markets and their actors. Top management must be committed to adopting agile strategies that enhance the development of innovative procedures and operating modes that anticipate the fulfil changing of both the economic environment and stakeholder’s requirements.

Planned change programs and rigid operating modes, optimized for efficiency not agility, are no longer adapted in our actual context of crises and continuous environmental changes. Management must rethink organizational structures, corporation functions and management practices such as planning, budgeting and the performance evaluation. Implementing an agile strategy is the process of turning a real-time decision into actionable outcomes for a specific context of change or uncertainty.

We distinguish three fundamentals sub-components concepts that support an agile strategy: the deployment of a continuous environment scanning, the promotion of a strategic commitment for change and the development of a continuous learning organization.

2.2.1. Continuous environment scanning:

The intensification of complex and chaotic contexts force organizations to run a systematic environment scanning. All the dimensions must be analysed: technological, social, economic and environmental aspects. The environment scanning is a valuable tool to management, allowing them to make decisions influenced from trended analysis of various factors that impact

the decisions-making process. It contributes in creating adapted action plans to address the unpredictable events and appropriating resources for those plans. It affords a quality data through different contexts and times.

The overall objective is to facilitate the tracking of trends and changes in an organization's internal and external environment that will take part on its success. An effective environment scanning must consider a set of key indicators – internal and external- that have a potential impact in the interpretation of a context.

Figure n°3: The main factors to consider for an environment scanning

Source: Author

Environment in our context refers not only to actual or potential uncertainties related to crises, but also in broader evolution and trends in demographics, lifestyles, technology, politics and public policy...

2.2.2. Strategic commitment for change:

A strategic commitment for change is considered as the most important pillars to a successful implementation of change initiatives. According to Nohria and Beer (2000) [10], 70 percent of change programs fail because of lack of vision, trust and communication toward the organization's employees. A clear vision is a succinct statement of the daily work's objectives to achieve.

Top management must be committed to adopt a culture of change, across all the levels of the organization, in order to promote the development of new ways to leverage existing areas of

expertise so as to serve the changing environment's requirements (S.Meredith & D.Francis, 2000) [11].

Within the framework of organizational agility, a strategic commitment for change includes a communicated vision statements and involved employees in the decision-making process. We identify four key factors for an effective commitment to change:

- Establish a clear shared vision with stakeholders.
- Leverage a change management timeline that includes the actions to follow before, during and after a change.
- Support employees and encourage them to new ways of doing business.
- Provide the opportunity to discuss about the challenges and possibilities associated to a new context.

2.2.3. Continuous learning organization:

The development of a learning organization is based on the potential to embody the notion that every experience, good or bad, is an opportunity to be grasped. The objectives are to convert the existing constraining conditions to beneficial conditions and to implement changes in timely manner.

According to Taheri (2007) [12] a learning organization is a laboratory to test, transmit and relate the experiences to the goals. Indeed, they create continuously new perspectives and extend all the levels and domains of the organization throughout interaction and coordination.

The characteristics of learning organizations include:

- Developing agile and consolidated ways of doing thing,
- Providing employees with sufficient information to develop their realistic decision-making capacity
- Analysing projects and actions feedbacks to identify improvements
- Packaging experiences to ensure their use in future contexts
- Encouraging group work and cooperation
- Transmitting information to internal and external stakeholders and learning from failures

For the development of our organizational agility framework, we get inspired from the OODA Loop Model (P.B. Osinga, 2007) [13] to illustrate the steps to follow for a continuous learning process in developing agile strategies.

Table 2: Mapping the learning process for the deployment of an agile strategy

Steps	Activities	Attributes for organizational agility
Observe	-Collect external information -Understand actual context and emerging situations -Sense the interaction with the environment	-Environments scanning
Orient	-Analyze practices, problems, and recommendations -Link the previous experiences and actual practices to the new collected information. -Develop situational awareness	-Identify suitable practices -Adjust an agile Scoreboard
Decide	-Define models needed to achieve the goal -Set adapted objectives for improvement -Use an agile scorecard to understand if the new actions support the strategy	-Select suitable practices to deploy
Act	-Communicate decisions -Collect measurement data and provide feedbacks	-Evaluate and Learn knowledge and beliefs. -Improve the agility of processes, methods and operating modes.

2.3. Agile processes and procedures

This pillar concerns the ways works are planned, performed and concluded within all the levels of the organization. The focus is on the practices and procedures of the organization aiming toward organizational agility. The structure is important to analyse because it is the guiding framework that influence and drives the vision and establishes the communication channels for an effective responsiveness and competency. Organizational agility starts with the forced change throughout factors from the environment. Once the change is sensed and analysed, decisions-makers take inventory of the current operating modes and procedures within the organization. Flexibility is needed for an increasing sought-after competitive advantage in today's fast-paced environment. The agile procedures are the practices and actions that lead to the improvement of the interaction between employees, and the timely dissemination of the information. Management must focus on performance and quality rather than strict processes and adherence to a fixed plan. It is more about to eradicate barriers that prevent objectives to be achieved. Therefore, plan daily status check is an effective way to guarantee that all the employees have the information they need for their work and keep projects moving coherently.

Management must also embrace an agile methodology that suits the need of the organizations and fits their resources. Transforming continuously a work environment promote a better tolerance for change and preparation for unpredictable situations.

2.4. Agile Linkages

The current business environment requires an extreme flexibility and nimbleness in executing works, making decisions and concluding projects. There are multiple challenges to seize while performing and managing projects, and also various threats to avoid. For that, organizations must have agile talented human resources to support and execute effectively the required actions to take. They must also conclude agile contracts to increase the cooperation with stakeholders and ensure various communication channels for the flexible dissemination of the information.

2.4.1. Agile HR

Fluids procedures require high levels of technical and personal competencies. Organization must recruit employees with deep skills and specialists with broad exposure to challenging situations. These require a good staffing, adapted training, reward for competencies and performance feedbacks. Employees must have the ability to shuffle work around the organization when the objectives or focuses change.

There are some principles to develop for agile employees:

- Cooperation: Groups are faster solving problems than individuals. It improves a synergy rather than a limited on sight opinion.
- Feedbacks as a fuel to learning: we recommend to use rapid and constant feedbacks on all the works done within the organization. It is about to study what creates efficiency and ensures agility every day.
- Appreciate deep knowledge: Staff the best expert to tackle the most complex and wicked situations.
- Daily-alignment: Devote a daily meeting to inspect the evolution of the action and to assess their execution.
- Decentralize power: organizations must tend to provide lower-level employees the authority to make decisions. It improves their motivation and implication on the decision-making process. Moreover, it allows a faster response to an immediate critical problem, especially in times of crises. The actions to take can be executed swiftly without requiring too much time to be approved and executed.

2.4.2. Agile contracts:

Agile contracts are changing the way in which contracts are drafted, negotiated and managed. Considering current time of crises and uncertainties, supply chains are complex and depends on multiple variable factors. Organization must rethink its contractual rigid clauses by transforming them into agile clauses to consider, timely, the changing environment and its requirements.

Basically, there are three types of agile contracts:

- Target cost contract
- Incremental delivery
- Time and material agreement

In the first type of contract, contractors agree on a best estimated cost. During the execution of the work, the initial target cost can be adjusted by agreement between the concerned parties. Any saving or overruns between the actual cost and the fixed target cost are shared with a pre-defined ratio set out in the contract. The importance of this sort of contracts is to incentivize the parties to fulfil their contracts at a lower cost depending on the actual context and up-dated market's requirements.

As to the incremental delivery contract, they allow the parties to review contracts at designed points in the contract life style. The contractors fixe predetermined review points when parties can evaluate performance up to that point and decide whether they will modify the arrangement, continue as planned or conclude the project.

The last type of agile contract is the simplest. Time and material agreement consist to pay the supplier for the time spent creating the delivering service or product as well as the for the material used in its creation and delivery. The parties can implement a capped form of this agreement so that the total cost not exceed the an upper-limit. This sort of contracts encourages efficiency and protects from excessive cost overruns regarding the contexts and situations.

Agile contracts increase collaboration and coordination between stakeholders. The projects are easily managed in shorter sprints and flexible with the changing circumstances.

2.4.3. Communication:

Flexible decision-making process, agile linkages and implicated stakeholders are effective only through a pratique implementation of various communication channels. A formal strategic communication facilitates clarity of the organization's strategic objectives and the transparency of the sense making behind the adopted planned actions as well as the context of different existing managerial functions.

We distinguish three primary types of internal communication channels: Top-down, Horizontal and bottom-up. Undoubtedly, an agile organization must be able to combine these three communication methods to guarantee an open and multi-directional communication within all the organization levels.

The first method is the traditional canal of communication used to be adopted by large firms. The top-down communication is when the information is flowing from upper-level management to the lower level of the organization. This type is binding because of its singularity of direction. The two other methods are more effective in boosting organizational agility. The horizontal communication enables inter-connection between all the departments and an effective exchange of information (Shill, et al., 2018) [14].

Finally, the Bottom-up communication affords strong commitment of all the levels of organization toward the enforcement of the strategies. It is not only about becoming more flexible, but also about facilitating a change through the whole organization.

In the main, a strategic communication is a key pillar to adopt an organizational agility through its following main roles:

- Communicate and enhance the strategic vision
- Manage perception and relationships with the stakeholders
- Create a new mindset and competencies among employees
- Enable functions and business units to become more agile by providing the necessary tools and digital platforms
- Adapt and harmonize the structures and the operating modes
- Manage Knowledge and shared experiences about contexts that required agility

2.5. Investing in BIG DATA and IT systems

To support agility, businesses must orchestrate their information systems with high concern. The actual pandemic crises and other recent financial crises have increased the reliance of the organization on using technologies as ERP, Internet of things, cloud computing, digital banking, e-commerce and other digital transformation.

The challenge is about surfacing the right information to the right concerned people, at the right time as we treated in the other pillars. The most quickly informed organizations will most be agile in facing the situation.

The use of Big DATA offers new economic commodities to respond to customer's changing requirements and the dynamic competitive environment (M. Ghasemaghahi & G. Calic, 2019) [15].

Organizations that use BIG DATA and IT systems have the ability to quickly sense, probe and act to capture opportunities in a changing and complex environment.

In fact, agile transformation can't happen without an IT system that is seamlessly integrated within all the levels of the organization. It also must make available the strategic information to all the concerned stakeholders in order to respond and adapt faster to the changing requirements.

For example, Web 2.0 Learning uses different technologies such as social networking, podcasting, cloud computing ...Flexible Data processing and IT systems provide save costs in storing and analysing large amount of data. With Digital Data analytics, top management can fuel better and faster decision-making process and anticipate future outcomes and results.

There are also new technologies as Blokchain that has the potential to store information and connect all the parties concerned by the project to access to data and track goods across the world. The benefits ok Blockchain technology is transparency, speed and security. Especially when it involves various parties such as suppliers, carriers, authorities, banks ... By ensuring security and trust within a transaction, there is no need to verify the authenticity of the documents and information.

But the challenge is to set a collaborative approach that include all the pillars for agility to be able to embrace this new technology along all the levels of the organization. Related to this, we recommend a common agreement on standards of work and the adoption of agile contracts.

Nowadays, all the organizations are jumping to BIG DATA, but some are having much better outcomes and results. That is why organizations must be aware of the importance to adapt their use as needed to take full advantage of the applied technology.

Organizations must provide adequate storage solutions and processing power to central servers for a dynamic memory that supports the amount of analytical DATA that transcend the organization. In addition to that, the right training of the employees that use the technology and adequate resource for implementation.

The conceptual framework of organizational agility is an attempt to give a simplified, easily applied but non-exhaustive representation of the most endorsed aspects of agility within an organization:

Figure n° 4: The fundamentals concepts for an organizational agility in time of crises

Source: Author

Conclusion

Organizational agility has become a competitive advantage for organizations to succeed in the actual environment characterized by unpredictable and sudden changes. This paper proposes an organizational agility framework that is grounded on fundamentals interrelated pillars.

Our proposed framework is different from the existing conceptual frameworks because it is adapted to both actual market's requirements and the new features in terms of performing activities in times of uncertainties and globalization. In effect, through the implementation of the ten enablers of organizational agility, the culture of adaptability will improve, and the employees will react more efficiently and quickly to changes.

The pillars are: the improvement of a culture of tolerance for change and ambiguity, the deployment of an agile strategy and processes, continuous environment scanning to analyse the change factors, the development of a strategic commitment for this change, the development of agile linkages within the organization, communication and finally, the implementation of adapted IT systems and BIG DATA to promote the transparency, security and dissemination of the information between stakeholders. The right data collection and the development of a learning organization, improve the agility to response timely to critical problems and to choose the appropriate actions to execute regarding the context.

As the market's requirements is constantly changing and the environment is unstable, an agile organization must continually apply it enablers and capabilities according to the proposed framework to adapt to these changes and flourish within all different conjunctures and contexts.

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